

METHODS OF ORGANIZING TRAINING WHEN TRAINING YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Annotation

The article discusses issues related to the methodology of training young volleyball players in modern conditions. The author focuses on the versatile physical and technical training of children based on mastering the elements of volleyball and other sports

Key words

Athletes, training, upbringing, volleyball, preliminary training, physical qualities of a child, sport, coordination character, physical training, game

The use of various sports games in the physical education system to achieve the goal of forming the foundations of physical and spiritual culture of the individual, increasing health resources as a system of values that are actively and long-term implemented in a healthy lifestyle. The role of sports games in solving the problems of physical education in a wide age range is great.

The effectiveness of sports games in promoting the harmonious development of personality is explained by their specifics: a deep versatile effect on the body of those involved, the development of physical qualities and the development of vital motor skills, accessibility for people of different ages and fitness, the entertainment of what is happening.

Sports games are widely represented in physical education in institutions of general and vocational education. In academic work, these are basketball, volleyball, handball, football, badminton, hockey, tennis and others. Sports games are widely used in the training of athletes of almost all sports, as an effective means of general physical training. Development of physical qualities and enrichment of the motor experience of athletes, especially young ones. In game sports, simpler games are also included among the means of general and special physical training.

Combining physical education with general physical training, we thereby carry out the process of comprehensive physical training, which has great training, tempering and wellness value, one of the sports games combining all physical qualities is volleyball.

Volleyball is an acyclic team game where muscle work is of a speed-strength, precision-coordination nature. With the small size and limitations of touching the ball, the execution of all technical and tactical elements requires precision and purposefulness of movements. The motor actions of volleyball players consist in a variety of lightning-fast starts and accelerations, in jumps, in a large number of explosive shock movements with a long, fast and almost continuous response to a changing environment, which places high demands on the physical fitness of volleyball players.

A qualitatively new level of development of a volleyball player requires a new level of development of the athlete's physical qualities (rule changes, recruiting teams with tall players; increasing the attacking potential due to fast movements and increased speed of performing techniques using the entire length of the net).

Volleyball techniques relate to complex coordination movements and therefore require careful preliminary training from the teacher-coach. Most coaches rely on their own experience in practical work with young volleyball players, recommendations from leading teachers and coaches, analysis of literary sources, publications on the World Wide Web. The flow of information that falls on the coach is very diverse and contradictory. The coach-teacher is faced with the task of making the right choice and making a decision that would contribute to the growth of the athletic skills of his students.

Volleyball can be called a universal means of physical education for all categories of the population - from preschool children to pensioners - to form the foundations of physical and spiritual culture of the individual, increase health resources, promote a healthy lifestyle [14]. The practical significance of the work lies in the fact that the results obtained will be applied in further work with a group of children, to improve their physical qualities, strengthen their health, and strive to educate a harmonious personality.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved:

To study the scientific and methodological literature on the chosen research topic. To develop a methodology for the development of physical qualities of young volleyball players.

To identify the effectiveness of the developed methodology experimentally.

Modern organizational and methodological approaches to determining physical fitness

The main feature characterizing a high level of general physical fitness is the ability to consciously control the movements of your body, achieving the

greatest results in the shortest possible time with the least effort. The health-improving effect of the development and formation of basic movements is well known, because a large number of muscle groups participate in these movements simultaneously, which helps to increase metabolism in the body, enhance the functional activity of internal organs, and improve the mobility of nervous processes.

The physical fitness of schoolchildren is characterized by two indicators:

The degree of mastery of the technique of movements.

The level of development of motor (physical) qualities

Physical fitness (motor) of students is improved as a result of learning in the classroom, but only under one condition: if the teacher teaches children to perform motor actions correctly, he educates their physical qualities. In physical culture as a scientific discipline, there are many definitions and concepts that reflect the essence of physical culture such as, "Physical culture", "sport", "physical education", "physical training", "physical development", and others.

The main and most general of them is the concept of "Physical culture", based on modern concepts of the theory of culture, it is possible to give the following definitions. Physical culture is a type of culture that represents a specific process and result of human activity, a means and method of physical improvement of people to fulfill their social responsibilities. An integrated approach asserts that when evaluating the sports and training activities of young volleyball players, it is important to study the components of sports training in both training and competitive activities. This makes it possible to consider the training of athletes from different points of view. They identify the following components and indicators in assessing the training activities of athletes: technical and tactical (arsenal of equipment and tactics, applicability of technical and tactical arsenal, effectiveness of game actions); special physical (explosive force, reaction speed, visual orientation, observation); psychological (moral and volitional qualities).

A systematic approach suggests that when evaluating sports and training activities, it is necessary to shift the main focus from physical training to the factors that ensure the effectiveness of this training.

These are tactical preparedness (the volume of tactical actions, the quality of their development, the applicability of tactics in the game;

the effectiveness of tactical actions); technical preparedness (the volume of techniques, the quality of development, the applicability of techniques in the game, the effectiveness of techniques);

physical fitness (the level of development of special physical qualities);
volitional preparedness (personality traits, motivation for classes, typological features of the nervous system, psychomotor qualities); theoretical preparedness (level of knowledge in the chosen sport);

integral preparedness (volume and effectiveness of technical and tactical actions); morphological signs (anthropometric indicators);

functional capabilities (the state of various body systems, visual, motor analyzers, neuromuscular apparatus);

the age gradation of volleyball players (the age of higher achievements, the age at certain stages of the long-term training system, the age of determining the game function, the age for starting specialized volleyball classes);

the experience of volleyball (individual, team).

A constructive approach says that in evaluating sports and training activities, the main thing is the organization of training cycles. Their analysis and operational adjustment make it possible to effectively influence the preparedness of young athletes for high results. They offer an assessment of the following types of training: technical (the number and variety of mastered techniques, the effectiveness of the use of technology), tactical (knowledge, skills and abilities in tactics, forecasting tactics, assessing the game situation, motor solution of tactical tasks, mental solution of tactical tasks), psychological (assessment of the most important psychological qualities for a game sport), physical (assessment of all basic physical qualities, efficiency of all organs and systems, coherence of their functions), integral (individual, group, team technical and tactical actions; the ability to maximize the mobilization of functional capabilities, the ability to switch maximum motor activity to periods of relative relaxation). Scientists also believe that the sports and training process must be properly organized within the framework of small (micro), medium (meso) and large (macro) cycles.

An individual approach in evaluating the sports and training activities of young volleyball players indicates that each athlete should be considered as a separate unit. V.S. Muntyan studies the components of various aspects of preparedness: technical (volume and versatility of equipment, stability of equipment in a competitive environment, resistance to external factors); physical (speed, strength, speed-strength, coordination qualities, flexibility, endurance, explosive strength); tactical (quantitative, qualitative components of tactical skill of athletes, versatility, rationality, effectiveness of tactical actions); psychological (personal, moral and volitional qualities, concentration of

attention, ability to control the level of arousal, degree of perception of movement parameters, ability to psychological regulation of muscular coordination, perception and processing of information, analytical activity, sensorimotor reactions, spatial-temporary anticipation); theoretical (special knowledge on the chosen sport, knowledge about the psychophysiological reactions of the athletes' body to loads, knowledge about the biomechanical characteristics of sports movements); functional capabilities of body systems.

The author believes that the assessment of the level of preparedness based on the results of all types of control (input, operational, current, intermediate, final) allows you to summarize their results and make up an individual cumulative indicator for each athlete characterizing his level of preparedness and the result of training activities at this stage.

As we can see, from the perspective of the presented views of scientists, a theoretical analysis of the problem of sports and training activities of young volleyball players showed that researchers consider the above-mentioned concept from different planes: some study this term from the perspective of sports training, others from the perspective of preparatory and training activities.

It is important to note that despite thorough research by scientists who sufficiently discuss the problem of sports and training activities of athletes, including sports and training activities of young volleyball players, there is no generally accepted definition of this concept in modern literature. Therefore, based on the analysis of the main scientific achievements, we are given the opportunity to define the term "sports and training activities of young volleyball players" and make several theoretical generalizations to understand the problem under study.

In our opinion, the sports and training activities of young volleyball players is a process aimed at improving the performance of all specialized qualities of young volleyball players necessary to achieve their goals. Within the framework of each of the above approaches in relation to the problem of evaluating the sports and training activities of young volleyball players, scientists pay special attention to the factors on which the result of training and later competitive activities depends.

Having considered the main approaches to evaluating the sports and training activities of young volleyball players, we believe that it is advisable to study the concept under study within the framework of systematic and integrated approaches, which together focus on the role of theoretical, technical,

tactical, psychological, physical characteristics of young volleyball players, which are quite necessary in the process of training and competitive activities.

Thus, based on the theoretical and methodological analysis of the study of the problem of sports and training activities of young volleyball players, we present the views of specialists on the definition and features of sports and training activities of young volleyball players, highlight the main scientific approaches to characterizing the evaluation of sports and training activities of young volleyball players, define the concept of "sports and training activities of young volleyball players."

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